

Ride 2Rail

**SOURCE CODE OF ALGORITHMS FOR OPTIMAL
SYNCHRONISATION OF SHARED-MOBILITY AND
MASS TRANSIT**
Deliverable D3.2

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of Shared-Mobility and Mass Transit

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the architecture of the Offer Enricher and Ranker (OER) developed in the scope of the RIDE2RAIL (R2R) project. RIDE2RAIL¹ (H2020-Shift2Rail-881825) has the overall objective of creating an innovative framework for intelligent multimodal mobility by facilitating the efficient combination of flexible and crowdsourced transport services, such as ridesharing, with scheduled transport. This framework will be integrated natively into existing collective and on-demand transport services, connecting and reinforcing the mobility offer with ridesharing services, especially in rural and low-demand areas. The goal of R2R is to facilitate access to high-capacity services (rail, bus, and other public transport services) thanks to easy-to-use multimodal and integrated travel planning, booking, ticketing, and payment features. The R2R framework will integrate real-time and diverse information about rail, public transport, and shared mobility in a social ecosystem.

This deliverable describes the results of Task 3.2 (T3.2), part of Workpackage 3 (WP3), where a novel system is introduced to rank multimodal travel solutions proposed through the Travel Companion (TC) based on the preferences and characteristics of the user making a mobility request. Users receive personalized travel offers whose ranking reflects their travel history. This work is built upon the conceptualization provided in D2.4 - “Final Conceptualization of Choice Criteria and Incentives,” and we continue in the same line of work of what has been done for the Offer Categorizer developed as part of Task T3.1 and described in D3.1 - “Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors.”

This task developed a state-of-the-art Offer Recommender, called THOR, to enable learning an optimal ranking of travel offers based on the following set of criteria:

- Travel offer characteristics: each travel offer is described along 11 different categories that cover several dimensions such as comfort, environmental friendliness, and health impact.
- Travel Incentives: in the context of R2R, an incentive is a mechanism to promote a shared ride as part of a door-to-door trip. They depend on the characteristics of the trip - for example, promoting the usage of eco-friendly modes of transport and shared rides.
- User’s preferences: the system will learn from past travel choices made by users

In practical terms, the Offer Enricher and Ranker receives a set of travel offers - i.e., the proposed travel solution for a mobility request made by an IP4 user - in TRIAS format, computes the availability of incentives, and outputs a personalized ranking of the travel offers, to be presented to the user.

¹ RIDE2RAIL website, <https://ride2rail.eu/>, accessed on 2022-01-13

Regarding the Offer Enricher and Ranker design, each software component has been developed as a microservice to facilitate its deployment in a production environment. Industry-standard practices were employed for the development. All the code that developed in the scope of this task will be publicly available on GitHub under the Ride2Rail organization.² This Deliverable is intended to be a companion to the software documentation available on GitHub under the RIDE2RAIL organization at <https://github.com/Ride2Rail>. This Deliverable describes the context and challenges faced during the development of the OER.

This deliverable is structured as follows: Section 3 presents the objectives of task T3.2 of RIDE2RAIL that is covered by this deliverable. Section 3 provides the background and context for the task, with a summary of the results from previous deliverables, covering the Offer Categorizer from D3.1, the definition of Travel Incentives from D2.4, and an overview of recommender systems in the context of mobility. Section 4 delves into the Offer Enricher and Ranker design, first by providing a general description of the main intuition at the basis of the architecture and then describing in detail the design decision taken, accompanied by their rationale. The development of the recommender component of the system (THOR) is described in detail. Section 5 describes the design of the travel incentive mechanism and its integration with the Agreement Ledger module. Finally, Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

² RIDE2RAIL GitHub organization, <https://github.com/Ride2Rail/>, accessed on 2022-01-13

Abbreviations and acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BSCV	Bayes Search Cross Validation
CFM	Calls for Members
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DBSCAN	Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise
DL	Dissemination and exploitation leader
DT	Decision Tree
DoA	Description of the Action
DSS	Decision Support System
EL	Ethical leader
EU	European Union
FS	Financial Statement
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
JU	Joint Undertaking
KNN	K-Nearest Neighbor
IFCD	Information-less Columns Drop
IP4	Innovation Programme 4
LR	Logistic Regression
OC	Offer Categorizer
OER	Offer Enricher and Ranker
OMR	Offer Enricher and Ranker
PC	Project coordinator
PM	Project manager
PMO	Project Management Office
PMT	Project Management Team
PO	Project Officer
POI	Point Of Interest

QAC	Quality Assurance Committee
RF	Random Forest
RS	Recommender System
S2R	Shift2Rail
SVC	Support Vector Classifier
TC	Travel Companion
THOR	The Hybrid Offer Ranker
TRIAS	Traveller Realtime Information and Advisory Standard
TL	Technical leader
TSP	Travel Service Provider
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work package leader

2. OBJECTIVE

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D3.2 “Source Code of Algorithms for Optimal Synchronisation of Shared-Mobility and Mass Transit” in the framework of the Task 3.2 of the RIDE2RAIL (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019). We report here the description of the task for clarity.

Task 3.2 Algorithms for optimal synchronisation of shared-mobility and mass transit

It will design and implement fair (non-discriminatory) context-aware composition of full end-to-end mobility solutions by assembling classified itinerary offers generated by multiple Travel Experts. The composition will implement new synchronization algorithms that will use estimated values of classified itineraries’ parameters to synchronize shared-mobility with rail and mass transit offers, including optimal matchings between drivers and riders to connect passengers with similar last-mile habits and similar needs. The algorithm will use the Travel Expert computed offer’s classification parameters, including their environmental categorization, in order to promote journeys with low emissions. Given a composed end-to-end solution including a shared route (e.g., in a car sharing trip to cover the last mile), this will be recommended to the users who may benefit from it, according to their needs, by ranking trips according to the contextual user preferences. These recommendations will be made efficient by grouping together users with similar influencing factors and needs, identified as the output of WP2. To make sure that the user preferences used for the trip ranking are up-to-date, this task will also develop mechanisms to mine user preferences actually selected in their history of choices, and adjust future trip rankings accordingly.

The output of this deliverable contributes as well to WP3 tasks T3.1-T3.5 of the RIDE2RAIL project (S2R-OC-IP4-01-2019).

3. BACKGROUND

This Section covers the background information for the Deliverable. This Deliverable is built upon the results of several previous outputs of the project. Section 3.1 reviews the output from D3.1 - “Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors,” and covers the Offer Categorizer, which receives the travel offer data from the S2R ecosystem and calculates category scores that are then fed into the Offer Enricher and Ranker covered by this Deliverable. Section 3.2 summarizes the definition and context for incentives defined in Deliverable D2.4 - “Final Conceptualization of Choice Criteria and Incentives.” Finally, Section 3.3 reviews the background for recommender systems for travel offers, which lie at the center of this task.

3.1. Offer Categorizer and Results from D3.1

The matching-and-ranking algorithm, the description of which is the main subject of the present document, is enabled by the Offer Categorizer (OC), which was thoroughly presented in Deliverable 3.1, “Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors”. Here follows a brief recap of this software component, such as to allow the reader a better understanding of its interconnections with the present document.

The purpose of the Offer Categorizer is to evaluate trip offers according to several dimensions, such as speed, price, comfort, environmental, and health impact. The outcome of this assessment is a series of quantitative scores associated with 11 categories. This categorization allows the matching-and-ranking algorithm to align each trip offer to users’ preferences over time, based on their past travel choices. Users will thus benefit from the enrichment of travel offers provided by the IP4 ecosystem and more personalized travel solutions over time.

Each category includes a series of Determinant Factors (DFs), which describe different characteristics of a specific aspect of the trip experience. For example, the “Quick” category includes the Determinant Factors “trip duration”, “waiting time”, “time to departure”, the “number of stops”, “distance”, and “traffic”. For this reason, the categorization requires, first, the retrieval and evaluation of the Determinant Factors and, hence, the combination of such features to obtain the category scores. The trip offers are defined in the TRIAS format.³

³ TRIAS, which stands for “Traveller Realtime Information and Advisory Standard,” is a transportation standard that has been developed in the scope of the research and standardisation project for public transport “IP-KOM-ÖV” and was introduced in 2014 as a standardized specification by the Verband Deutscher Verkehrsunternehmen.

The XSD specification of the TRIAS format can be found at <https://github.com/VDVde/TRIAS>.

TRIAS provides a wide-range list of functionalities, including station and location search, real-time departures, navigation, ticket price calculation, and malfunction reporting.

Delving deeper into the design and implementation of the system, the OC can be seen as the integration of the following components (see Figure 1):

- The OC-core, which is in charge of the management of the whole workflow; in particular, it is responsible of setting up the connections between the other components, combining their input and output, aggregating the Determinant Factors, carrying out the categorization of the offers and handling the errors that might occur at any point in the computation.
- The Offer Cache, which represents a shared data layer accessed by the different microservices composing the OC; it specifies the representation of multi-modal offers and the storage method of the Determinant Factors associated to each offer.
- The TRIAS extractor, that parses offers from TRIAS files, converts them to the Offer Cache schema and writes them into the cache.
- A series of Feature Collectors, each of which is responsible of retrieving a specific set of Determinant Factors from the parsed offer and returning them to the OC-core, which will later aggregate them and compute the normalized scores for the final categorization; examples of Feature Collectors are “time-fc”, which gathers “trip duration”, “waiting time”, “trip to departure”, “time of trip (rush vs non-rush hour)” or “active-fc”, which collects “bike/walk distance”, “total walk distance”, “total distance”, “bike/walk legs”.

Figure 1 Offer Categorizer Architecture

From a general perspective, the steps performed by the OC core can be summarized as follows:

1. The OC-core receives a TRIAS file describing a trip request.

2. The TRIAS extractor parses the data and writes it into the cache.
3. The feature collectors, in a parallel and asynchronous fashion that guarantees efficiency, retrieve all the relevant information from the trip data. Further information about the parallelization are covered in Appendix A.
4. When all feature collectors have finished their job, the OC-core aggregates the Determinant Factors, producing a score for each category.

Each software component belonging to the OC has been developed as a microservice, to facilitate its deployment in a production environment. We have used industry-standard practices for the development and all the code that we have developed in the scope of this tasks is already publicly available on GitHub under the Ride2Rail organization.

For further details on the category definition, the categorization algorithm, the software implementation and deployment, we refer the reader to Deliverable 3.1 (“Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors”).

3.2. Incentives

This section summarises the conceptualisation and research work surrounding the issue of offering incentives to ride-to-rail users i.e. the ways in which the R2R trip offer implementation incentivises travellers who choose to combine a shared ride to or from a transport hub. This research work was conducted and reported in deliverable D2.4 (Section 8.4). This section presents 1) the agreed definitions of incentives and the related concepts within the scope of the R2R project and 2) the catalogue of potential incentives that could be relevant for implementation in the R2R project 3) the selection and rationale for the final incentives to be implemented in the R2R project.

3.2.1. Definitions

An *incentive* is a method used by the R2R journey planner to promote one or more trip offers over others, and more particularly in the context of the R2R project, to promote a shared ride as part of a door-to-door trip. *Incentives mechanisms* consist of the technique used to promote an offer: these can be tangible or intangible. *Tangible incentives* consist of material or monetary benefits provided to the traveller, such as discounts on tickets, purchases or additional services, class upgrades, or tradable frequent-traveller points. *Intangible incentives* consist of soft measures and benefits, such as additional information relevant to the trip and the gamification of some aspects of the trip to increase interest, engagement, social status or even behaviour changes. Incentives are provided by incentive providers (usually the TSP but it can also be an external, governmental or non-governmental organisation). Finally, the applicability of a specific incentive for a specific trip by a specific traveller at a specific time is determined by the *incentive condition*, which is the outcome of a function combining trip offer and traveller needs into a single yes/no variable.

3.2.2. Catalogue

In order to narrow down and assess the attractiveness of various incentive options, D2.4 conducted a survey asking to rank between 1 to 5 which incentive techniques could most likely influence the traveller to chose a different trip option (see D2.4 appendix A for a list of choices presented in the survey). After integrating new options that were suggested as

part of the survey, the final list of potential tangible and intangible incentives was established in Table 10 of D2.4, reproduced below, in order of most to least attractive.

Table 1 Final catalogue of incentives (reproduces from Table 10 in D2.4)

Description	Type
Immediate price discount on a given travel offer	Tangible
Discounted or a free update of the travel class	Tangible
Discounts on the following purchases	Tangible
Ancillary services offered for free or discounted (e.g. snack, meal, entertainment system)	Tangible
Point Accrual associating points with travel offers, points earned can be converted to prizes (e.g., Loyalty programme)	Tangible
Provide to user information that can increase her/his awareness on the environmental sustainability of a travel offer (e.g. displaying CO2 emissions)	Intangible
Provide to the user additional material promoting a given travel offer, e.g., include in an offer the images of city monuments that can be spotted during the travel. This can support, e.g., to promote the usage of the bus over the underground, even if the second solution might be faster.	Intangible
Discounts on complementary services (e.g., hotel)	Tangible
Adopt a gamification strategy assigning badges to award the achievements of pre-defined goals (e.g. trying a ride-sharing solution for the first time, or choosing the solution with the lowest environmental impact)	Intangible
Assign points to the user for virtuous choices in travel solutions (e.g. environmentally sustainable) and set up a daily/weekly/monthly shared leaderboard (e.g. among friends)	Intangible
For-free insurance for health/travel issues (delays or cancelations)	Tangible
Free cancelation or changes	Tangible
For-free possibility to get on-board on historical or newly adopted means of transport	Tangible
Provide information on the applicability of security measures both related to Covid-19 like the commitment to maintain social distancing, and to the feeling of personal safety, such as the presence of security personnel.	Intangible

Perhaps unsurprisingly for some, tangible incentives significantly outscored intangible incentives in the survey, in that travellers seemed more interested in gaining an immediate and measurable reward, preferably a monetary one. Among non-financial incentives, additional trip information (including the environmental footprint of different offers) gathered the highest interest.

3.2.3. Selection and reflection for future research

Based on survey results and considering the requirements on the technical realisation, the R2R project narrowed the selection of incentive options to the following three tangible-only choices which are further used to demonstrate the mechanism of incentivisation:

Incentive 1 - upgrade of train seat class category,

Incentive 2 - 10% discount on the train ticket,

Incentive 3 - 20% discount on the train ticket.

This design choice was made in consideration for the implementability of the solution as well as for the possibility to easily translate the incentives as variables that can be used for modelling in machine learning models applied by the ranking algorithms. However a few notes of caution on these results must be said, which may open the door for research leading to an extended set of mixed tangible-intangible incentives in future iterations.

The issue of incentives is complex and very contextual, and therefore the issue of surveying potential travellers about incentives is also likely to be complex and contextual. In other words, the D2.4 survey has limitations due to boiling down this complex issue to a single question and 10 simple choices of incentives. In a broader context, research questions that would need to be answered, either based on literature reviews or targeted research, could be:

How can travel choice be nudged? Can incentives create durable behaviour change? What is the right mix of tangible and intangible incentives?

Theory of travel behaviour in the social sciences points at the risk that short-term monetary incentives can be effective in nudging a one-time decision, but to change behaviour generally requires changing habits and attitudes, which requires trying new options outside one's comfort zone that may be better triggered by a mix of tangible and intangible incentives[1].

How to properly assess the types of intangible incentives that an individual traveller could be sensitive to? How to design personalised intangible incentives that consider the travel context and traveller needs and characteristics in realtime?

Theory on psychological motivation to employee satisfaction in the workplace shows that once a certain salary level is reached, monetary considerations and tangible incentives become less relevant, whereas other more complex factors play a more important role, for example status, identity, gratitude and social recognition, flexibility and freedom etc[2]. In a similar way, cost and travel time savings are not necessarily the most important factors for all travellers and all trips. Travellers have preferences towards some types of travel modes and travel characteristics, which can change because of travel purpose and conditions (e.g. time constraints, whether travelling alone or accompanying someone), wider characteristics of the offer (e.g. trip duration, comfort factors, or even the weather), or the need to use travel time for something useful or simply preferring more enjoyable options[3].

In conclusion to this section, we concede that incentivisation in R2R is primarily understood as quantification and monetisation, but we are aware that this is a limitation due to a required simplification of the context to the journey planning situation. Embracing more complex incentive packages would require enlarging the context of travel to embrace wider considerations of human activities, which could help uncover more attractive and intangible incentives that those shortlisted here for implementation. This goes beyond the R2R scope and it would require a social science and interdisciplinary research approach combining psychology, travel behaviour, economics, as well as transport planning and engineering to achieve the higher degree of personalisation this approach would entail.

3.3. Overview of Recommender Systems for Travel Offers

This section discusses related works about Recommender Systems (RS) for travellers, and how they inspired the proposed methodology. To the best of our knowledge, most of the work focused on designing an RS for the tourist purposes where the system aims at recommending the most suitable destination to a traveler. However, we need to design an RS that ranks a set of travel offers given a mobility request by the user of our system. Section 3.3.1 explores various works to better understand the demographic data used by the related works. Section 3.3.2 discusses the state-of-the-art approaches employed for designing the RS in the travel domain. Finally, Section 3.3.3 aims at investigating papers which work on tackling the cold start problem. This section presents the state of the art of Recommender Systems for Travel Offers, but doesn't categorise the R2R system itself in one of the categories. One paragraph or sub-section at the end of 3.3 could help the reader understand the category of the R2R recommender system.

3.3.1. Methods for collecting implicit users' preferences

This section covers the state-of-the-art of methods used to learn implicit users' preferences in tourism recommender systems.

Traditional tourism recommender systems are primarily designed for recommending travel destinations to travelers. Therefore they mainly employ demographic data related to the opinions of the users about the destinations.

Ng et al. [4] implemented a hybrid recommender system based on images and text obtained from the Airbnb dataset for the advertised accommodation offers in Hong Kong. Around 1 million image-related features are extracted from a total of 110,572 accommodations' images for calculating the similarity. Using a context-aware agent-based methodology [5], the proposed system predicts users' ideas while viewing images during online shopping. The information extracted from the images shared by the users allows the estimation of their interests.

Sebasti et al. [6] developed a framework that collects user profiles by requiring users to enter their details and general preferences and asking them to introduce their specific preferences for the current visit. Then, the system generates a list of activities that are likely of interest to the user. A subsystem will calculate the recommendations based on the profiles and the current preferences. The third step is to compute the tourist agenda with the selected activities of the previous step. At this stage, the planning module schedules the list of recommended places according to their temporal characteristics and the user's restrictions. The final step is to process the user feedback, and the system will keep learning the user's decisions.

The proposed method by Fang et al. [7] automatically generates temporal feature vectors from a collection of documents based on Wikipedia and Twitter. These temporal features of Points Of Interest (POIs) include seasonal attractions such as water sports, snow festivals, and the viewing of scarlet maple leaves. All the vectors will be recorded in the database, and the attractions will be recommended by matching the users' requests and the vectors.

Coelho et al. [8] proposed a travel RS based on social media analysis. Travel-related tweets will be used to personalize recommendations regarding places of interest for the user.

Firstly, they categorize POIs as historical buildings, museums, parks, and restaurants; then, they build a machine learning classification model to classify the tweets. The tweets are used to personalize the recommendations according to the (POIs). For having a better-personalized model, travel-related tweets of the user's friends and followers are also mined. Farani et al. [9] explore a user profiling process that consists of four scenarios:

- Inscription: The user explicitly indicates their interests to the system.
- Social login: Instead of creating a new login account, the user can use a third-party account such as Facebook. Then, the current information in this account also can be used in the system.
- Consultation even without login: It relies on the observation and analysis of user behaviors. In this way, the system will implicitly collect users' information in the backend.
- Context: It is based on the integration of contextual information to generate dynamic visit schedules.

The system also contains a repository of services for storing the information on the tourist services, a contextual meta-model for analyzing all the input data, a hybrid filtering process for storing the list of items with users' appreciation degree, and a trip planner for correlating all the choices in the form of a trip.

Basile et al. [10] proposed a system to understand if the users' preferences explicitly match with their behavior. This type of model can keep improving the accuracy of understanding the users' preferences. The system is composed of the following phases: first, it builds user profiles, i.e., general descriptions of the users based on their travel preferences; second, it builds profiles using evaluation data collected after the actual travels; finally, they match the before- and after-travel user profiles. In this way, they can characterize users' behaviors at an aggregated level and find patterns that can reveal valuable information about users' travel choices by considering different travel modes and a complete definition of travel time. Consonni et al. [11] collect the travel-centered mobility data via crowdsourcing. Crowdsourcing was seen as a powerful tool to collect feedback on the travelers' value of travel time and their mobility choices. The travel time is analyzed from a traveler's perspective. The user is asked about which activities they have performed during the trip, which factors have influenced their trip positively or negatively. After analyzing the data, they were able to change the perspective from considering travel time as a spent, worse, wasted to the time that other activities can be characterized. Understanding the travelers and their choices according to the value of their travel time can help the system learn the preferences more accurately.

Boratto et al. [12] analyze and characterize user behavior during journey planning to get insights from different perspectives related to trip search options, i.e., both sorting and selection actions. While selecting different travel offers, the system can rapidly learn more about the users' preferences. We need to recommend users a complete travel offer in our work, which contains almost all the information during a trip. Besides the places, the travel offer also contains the transportation mode, services, timetable, etc. Therefore, we cannot only consider the data that are useful for predicting the target places. All the data that may help us figure out the users' contexts can be meaningful for our system.

3.3.2. Review of recommender models

Recommender systems are usually classified into one of the following categories: content-based, collaborative, or hybrid [13].

- Content-based recommendations: The user will be recommended items similar to the ones they preferred in the past.
- Collaborative recommendations: The user will be recommended items that people with similar tastes and preferences liked in the past. A typicality-based collaborative filtering method is discussed in [14].
- Hybrid approaches: These methods combine collaborative and content-based methods.

A more comprehensive study of all types of methods used in tourism RS is provided by Chen et al. in [15]. Moreover, they used the recommended projects to solve the classification problem. The criteria take into account different items when evaluating products and services. As for the items related to tourism, the personalized recommendations include individual recommendations about attractions, hotels, restaurants, flights, etc., as well as combining the recommendations on destinations, travel plans, travel packages of products, activities, and services. They also studied the current status of academic researches on RS in the travel domain. The result revealed that the relevant literature is mainly distributed in computer science, tourism management, and the inter-discipline of information technology and tourism, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), semantic network, user modeling, machine learning, data mining, Decision Support System (DSS), adaptive control, information retrieval, man-machine interaction, etc.

Valliyammai et al. [16] explored a model-based collaborative filtering to make the predictions. Their work takes advantage of the fuzzy c-means algorithm [17] for data clustering and A-priori algorithm [18] for data classification. Then the proposed system can provide a high degree of personalized recommendations.

Sebasti et al. [6] utilize a hybrid approach to build an RS. The method employs first classifies the user into different categories like “Person with Children”. Then, a content-based approach will be used to recommend more cities according to their histories. Finally, a filter will select the proper cities based on the current request. However, the system only provides specific items to the user, but we need to recommend a complete trip plan rather than the location recommendation.

Kbaie et al. [19] explored another hybrid tourism RS. The system mainly focuses on recommending the tourist activities in a particular destination in a personalized way. This method can help the TSP to design the corresponding activities in travel offers.

Lorenzi et al. [20] divide each recommendation into different travel services, and each different agent (that works cooperatively) performs the travel services. During the recommendation cycles, agents become experts in specific travel services, and each agent has specific knowledge about travel services in its knowledge base. The interaction among the agents results in better recommendations. An excellent travel offer will be generated by combining all recommended services by different agents in this method. The results may be suitable for one user, but can be quite different for different users, which increases a lot the time and money costs for the TSPs.

He et al. [21] propose an optimized RS for recommending POIs. They aim to recommend a sequence of POIs instead of a single POI. They use a trip generation to schedule the best routine that contains all the points in the POIs sequence above.

Tulashvili et al. [22] develop an intelligent way to construct an optimal sequence of tourist sites to be recommended. This method helps the travelers to get their travel plan, but the problem is that the TSP may not set up this travel offer for one traveler only, because the TSP needs to consider more constraints than the user request, such as the budget, cooperation company, etc.

3.3.3. Tackling the cold start problem

The system should have access to a sufficient number of user's records before a content-based recommender system can understand the user's preferences and provide the user with reliable recommendations. Therefore, a new user, having very few records, would not receive accurate recommendations. The dependency on the existence of historical data is known as the "cold start problem" [23].

[24] and [25] explore various techniques for determining the best offers for a new user. These techniques employ strategies based on travel offer popularity, travel offer entropy, user personalization, and combinations of the above.

Recommending a new user with some top popular offers is another common approach; it can increase the user's purchase possibility, but decrease the personalization. Collaborative methods can help to improve personalization, but the recommendations' precision might be quite low.

The cold start problem of traditional RS is also addressed by Sang and Vishwakarma [26] and Guo [27]. Sang and Vishwakarma developed a system that uses an Item KNN classifier to divide the different groups of items with the help of similarity formulas based on the similarity between items. When the system has no information about the new user, Item KNN provides the users with recommendations for the item with the help of other item groups in the system and finds the K-closest item.

The module described in this deliverable uses a unique way to combine collaborative and content-based methods. It does not aim to find a similar user for a new one, but tries to find a group of users similar to them, instead. It does not directly recommend new users the travel offers that have been bought by a similar group. However, it uses a content-based method to build the recommender model for the group and use the model to predict the new user's recommendations.

Ghodsad & Chatur [28] also proposed a similar solution for building an RS for a group of travelers. They explored a similar profile-wise group detection method and a social behavior-wise group detection method. The system will then fetch a group of similar users every time it receives a new user, decreasing the performance of the tool, hence this approach is not conducive to reuse for our system. Cluster algorithms can help us group all the users according to their profiles, and the model based on these algorithms can predict the cluster of a new user.

At its core, the Matcher and Ranker uses an approach that combines collaborative and content-based methods to develop a novel *hybrid* approach. Given a new user, the

Matcher and Ranker does not aim to find a single similar user, but it looks for a group of users with similar characteristics, instead. Then, it does not directly recommend new users the travel offers that have been bought by their similar groups. Rather, it uses a content-based method to build the recommender model for the group and uses the model to predict the new user's recommendations.

4. MATCHER AND RANKER DESIGN

This section describes the main elements of the Offer Matcher and Ranker (OMR) module. We also use the name Offer Enricher and Ranker to talk more generally about the system that combines the Offer Categorizer (OC) and Offer Matcher and Ranker (OMR). In particular, Section 4.1 provides an overview of the module, and outlines its internal components. Section 4.2 briefly lists the technologies used to realize the module. Finally, Section 4.3 describes in some detail the approach used by the OMR to determine which travel offers travellers are more likely to buy, and rank them accordingly. More precisely, Section 4.3 describes the two main activities carried out by the core of the OMR: the *learning* of the user preference models, and their use in the *ranking* of the travel offers according to the likelihood that the user will buy them.

4.1. General Overview of the Architecture of the System

Figure 2 Overview of the architecture of the system.

The diagram on Figure 2 shows the general architecture of the system. We decided to build the Offer Matcher and Ranker (OMR) around the Offer Cache, which is the storage component. We save the parsed input into the Offer Cache and we also save the output of each subcomponent. This diagram should be read left-to-right and top-to-bottom, components at the same height can be executed in parallel.

The Offer Enricher and Ranker (OER) component, which exposes a dedicated REST API, receives a set of travel offers from the Shopping Orchestrator for each request performed by the user.

The data received are forwarded to the Offer Enricher and Ranker Core or OER core. This is the central component in charge of orchestrating the system and controlling every other piece. Its responsibilities include setting up the connections between the different subcomponents, invoking them and combining their outputs.

The first component to be invoked in the process is the TRIAS extract, which parses offers. We defined as Offer Parser a component that is able to parse offers in a given format, extract information and store them in the Offer Cache (shared data layer) according to the internal data model defined for the OC. The Offer Parsers implemented in Ride2Rail are described in Section 5.4 of D3.1 "Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors," while the internal data model defined for the Offer Cache is described in Section 5.2 of D3.1. An Offer Parser may require a Feature Enricher subcomponent, possibly connecting to external services, to compute/retrieve information about the offer. The OER core will firstly call the TRIAS extractor component. This module is responsible for parsing the TRIAS offers, converting them to the Offer Cache schema and storing the information there.

Once this procedure is completed, the OC core will call different submodules:

1. *Data Provider*, the role of this component is to retrieve information from the Cloud Wallet (CW), which is part of the IP4 ecosystem. In particular, the Data Provider will query the CW to retrieve the profile and preferences of the user who made the mobility request which is being process so that the results of the OER are personalized.
2. *Incentive Provider*, the role of this component is to test the characteristics of the user-offer combination for incentives, as described in Section 3.2. This component interacts with the Agreement Ledger module, which is being developed as part of Tact T3.5 "Ride-Sharing Agreements Ledger Module."
3. *Offer Categorizer Core*, is the orchestration component for the offer categorization task. The OC core will interact with several subcomponents that we named Feature Collectors. Each feature collector has the ability to extract the data it needs from the Offer Cache and use that from that compute a set of related determinant factors needed for the categorization. We designed Feature Collectors as independent microservices to enable the parallelisation of the processing required. Finally, the OC core will be able to aggregate accordingly the different determinant factors to compute the membership of each offer considering each offer category. The architecture of the Offer Categorizer subsystem is described in detail in Section 5.4 of of D3.1 "Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors."

Once every submodule has completed its corresponding computations, they will write the results back to the Offer Cache. The Offer Cache is described in detail in Section 5.2 "Software technologies" of Deliverable D3.1 "Quantitative Estimate of Service Quality Factors."

The last component to be called is the OMR Recommender, which is named THOR, which will use all the data collected so far - i.e. covering user preferences, incentives, and offer categorization - to produce a personalized ranking of the offers for the user making the

mobility request, which also takes into account the availability of incentives. This component is described in more detail in Section 4.3.

4.2. Technologies used

Building a system such as the OER requires adaptable and modern technologies. We build upon the experience matured with building the Offer Categorizer. The technologies used in developing and implementing the OMR are the same used in Task 3.1 “Development of algorithms to propose quantitative estimates”:

- Docker,⁴ an open platform containerization platform.
- Flask,⁵ a micro web framework written in Python,
- Redis,⁶ an open-source, in-memory key-value store.

Refer to Section 5.1 “Software technologies” of Deliverable D3.1 “Quantitative Estimate of Service Quality Factors” for a detailed description.

4.3. THOR

The core of the Matcher and Ranker, named THOR⁷ (The Hybrid Offer Ranker) aims at providing ranked travel offers to Travel Companion (TC) users according to their contextual preferences. *Figure 3* provides a high-level overview of the main components for learning the users’ preferences and rank the travel offers accordingly.

⁴ <https://www.docker.com>, Docker website, visited on 2021-12-23.

⁵ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/>, Flask website, visited on 2021-12-23.

⁶ <https://redis.io/>, Redis website, visited on 2021-12-23.

⁷ The source code of THOR is available in the following repository: [HYPERLINK "https://github.com/Ride2Rail/Learner_Ranker"](https://github.com/Ride2Rail/Learner_Ranker)

Figure 3 Overview of the main elements of THOR

The request and user profiles will be collected when TC users send a mobility request through the S2R ecosystem. For each of the travel offers built by the S2R ecosystem, the Offer Categorizer (OC) module - see Section 3.3.1 of D3.1 “Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors” - provides scores for the following categories: *fast, reliable, cheap, comfortable, door-to-door, environmentally friendly, short, multitasking, social, panoramic, and healthy*. The OC module also extracts some details specific to each leg from each travel offer. Particularly, the extracted leg-level information include: *transportation mode, seat type, carrier, and length*. In the rest of this section we refer to the offers with added information about categories and leg-level information as *enriched offers*.

The enriched offers are combined with the user’s most recent profile information to build the ranker’s input data. The *ranker* uses the *personal contextual preference* model of the user - given by the *learner* - to predict if they will buy the travel offer or not. The same procedure is applied for all received travel offers. In the next step, the ranked list of travel offers are sent back, through the S2R ecosystem, to the user.

The S2R ecosystem keeps track of the purchases made by the user, and this information is used to update the user’s historical data by tagging purchased offers with a suitable flag. The learner module uses these new records to update the user’s contextual preference model. Suppose a user has a number of records in their historical database that is below a given threshold (which is a parameter for the whole system), for example, 100. In this case, we say that the user is a “Cold User”, and we train their model based on the data of other travelers with similar profiles and preferences. Notice that we call “user” a customer with adequate historical data. On the other hand, we refer to users without any historical data as *new user*.

4.3.1. Data Preprocessing

Whether collected by the system or from the user’s updated profile and requests, the user’s preferences are stored in the database in text (CSV) form. The learning module can use the information in the database only after the former has been suitably formatted. Because THOR mainly uses data in textual form, this type of translation is always necessary during

the recommender model training phase, cluster model training phase, and request-response phase. Hence, data preprocessing is performed according to the steps depicted in Figure 4, which are overviewed in the rest of this section.

Figure 4 Data preprocessing steps

One-Hot Encoding: This step translates the raw textual data into a numerical one-hot version. All the Null data are also changed to zero value, and only the valid columns are kept.

Information-less Columns Drop (IFCD): The IFCD stage aims to delete all the columns that have the same value in the dataset. For instance, if the user has never changed their hometown, we can delete it because this feature means nothing for our system. Many columns have no useful information and deleting them all substantially speeds up the training phase.

Data Normalization: Our data has many features, and each feature will affect whether this offer will be bought or not. However, the scales and magnitudes of these features are not the same. When predicting the recommendation results, if the original data values are used directly, their degree of influence would be different. Different features can have the same scale through a normalization process, thus every feature will have the same influence on the result.

4.3.2. Learner Module

The *Learner* is one of the fundamental blocks in the whole system, and it constantly keeps learning users' preferences and build the most recent contextual preference model for each user separately. Figure 5 details the logic control of the learner module.

Figure 5 Workflow of Learner's module

A client (e.g., an administrator) can manually update models (using a suitable primitive) or set a regular schedule (e.g., once a week) to initiate this process automatically. Before training the model, the administrator can choose to update the current user or not, read all the users' current profiles, and take them all into one table as the input data to the cluster training system. The administrator can also upload the other users' profile data, as supplied by the third parties, to help the system train a better model at the first stage.

For a cold user, the administrator can decide to retrain the cluster model by setting a suitable parameter (*reClusterTag*) to true, and the retraining process will also be completed when the system does not find the cluster model. During the cluster model training phase, all the users' profiles will be collected and sent to the `API_CLUSTER_TRAINING` algorithm; the cluster model and recommender model for each cluster are preserved in the system. These models are associated with the cold user after getting their cluster number; in this way we can implement the idea of building the cold user's model by training models based on the historical data other similar travelers.

For a normal user (with enough historical data), the administrator can use this interface to train or retrain the user's model by running algorithm `API_CLASSIFIER_TRAIN`, and the user's best model will be saved in the system.

The algorithm in Figure 6 provides the pseudo-code of the Learner module. The Learner will update the user profile, if needed, and use a different way to train the model according to the user type.

Input: username; new profile (optional) if user is a new user; reCluster tag declares whether the administrator wants to update the cluster model.

Output: The Model file for the user will be saved in the predefined path.

```
1: function MODELTRAIN(username,reCluster tag, (new profile))
2:   user type ← check the number of user's historical records(username)
3:   cluster model exist tag ← check whether the cluster model exist or not
4:
5:   if user new profile is given then
6:     user profile table in data ← update the database with new profile
7:   end if
8:
9:   if user type is old user then
10:    recommender model ← train model(username,new profile)
11:  else
12:    if cluster model not exist OR retrain cluster tag is True then
13:      cluster model ← train cluster model
14:      predefined model ← train model for each cluster
15:    end if
16:    recommender model ← copy model(predefined model)
17:  end if
18:  model file ← save model (recommender model)
19: end function
```

Figure 6 Learner algorithm

The rest of this sections provides the implementation details concerning the training of a cluster model and training the contextual preference model.

Cluster Training for New User

The system divides all users into different groups and sets a *predefined model* for each group to solve the cold user problem. These predefined models will be used to make predictions for the cold user. Figure 7 details how cluster training function solves this problem. The function also supports using the data supplied by the administrator; otherwise, the system will automatically fetch the current profiles of all valid users in the database.

Figure 7 Cluster model training process

The pseudo-code of the cluster model training algorithm is shown in Figure 8. In a nutshell, the algorithm first computes the best parameters' setting and uses it to fit the cluster model. Then, it gathers the data for each cluster and trains the predefined model for them.

Input: Set search range in range define function
Output: Cluster model saved in file; and predefined recommender model of each cluster

```

1: function PARAMETERS TUNING
2:   search range  $\leftarrow$  parameters range define
3:   smaller K range  $\leftarrow$  Elbow method(KMeans, search range)
4:   best K, score  $\leftarrow$  silhouette coefficient(KMeans, smaller K range)
5:   best setting, score  $\leftarrow$  silhouette coefficient(DBSCAN, search range)
6:   best setting  $\leftarrow$  max score (KMeans, DBSCAN)
7:   return best parameter setting
8: end function
9:
10: best parameter setting  $\leftarrow$  parameters tuning()
11: data  $\leftarrow$  gather all users' profiles in system
12: cluster model, model info  $\leftarrow$  model fit and save(best parameters, data)
13:
14: for cluster  $\in$  all clusters saved in model info do
15:   cluster history data  $\leftarrow$  merge all the users' data in the cluster
16:   cluster model  $\leftarrow$  train and save recommender model(cluster data)
17: end for

```

Figure 8 Cluster model training algorithm

More precisely, before fitting the model, the system finds the best parameters by using the *PARAMETERS TUNING* function. To do so, the first step is to define the search range for each parameter in different algorithms. THOR uses two well-known clustering algorithms, *K-means* [29] and *Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN)* [30]. In THOR, these algorithms are realized through the *sklearn.cluster* [31] library. For the *K-means* algorithm, we employ the *elbow* method to check a large range of the best number of clusters and then use a more precise method called *silhouette coefficient*

to find the best parameters in the smaller range given by the elbow diagram. For the DBSCAN algorithm, we set a large range for the *eps* and *min_samples* parameters, narrow the range by checking the best score and changing tolerance value, and reduce the step to get a more accurate range value. After obtaining the best parameters, we can use the *ClusterModelFit* function to generate the cluster model and use functions *KMeans.labels* and *DBSCAN.labels* to get the user lists in each cluster.

Next, we combine the historical records of all users in each cluster to get the knowledge base of that cluster, and use this data to run *API_CLASSIFIER_TRAIN* and get the cluster's recommender model. Finally, we use the cluster model to predict the new user's cluster and associate that cluster's recommender model with the new user, thus solving the cold user problem.

User Recommender Model Training

Classifier training is the core function for building the recommender models for users, and its basic logic is defined in Figure 9. Figure 10, instead, shows the pseudo-code of cluster model training algorithm. This module first computes the best parameters' setting and then uses it to fit the recommender model.

Figure 9 Workflow of the classifier model training function

Input: username; Set search range in range define function
Output: recommender model and related info saved in file

```
1: user history data ← fetch from database(username)
2: train data ← data preprocessing(user history data)
3: search range ← parameters range define
4:
5: for alg. ∈ [KNN, SVC, DT, LR, RF] do
6:   temp best model,score ← BSCV(alg.,train data, search range)
7:   best model ← compare model score
8: end for
9: model file ← save the model in file(best model)
```

Figure 10 Cluster model training algorithm

First, the module fetches all historical travel offer records of the user for which the model is to be trained, including the information of whether the offer was bought or not bought or not, to create the training dataset. After performing one-hot encoding, dropping information-free columns, and normalization, we obtain a well distributed numerical metric. This data is used to find the best algorithm and the best parameters, which are then in turn used to compute the final model to be associated with the user.

The module assumes that each travel offer has been categorized as “bought” or “not bought”. Thus, recommending a user some new travel offers turns into a simple classification problem, which classifies all the records of new travel offers and current profile as “buy” or “not buy”. The system predicts the probability of buying the offer as the score of this offer and ranks offers according to their score.

To build user preference models, THOR uses some popular predictive algorithms, and in particular the KNN [32], SVC [33], DT [34], RF [35], and LR [36] classification algorithms provided by the *sklearn* [31] library.

Since the performance can differ significantly between different classification algorithms for a given dataset, THOR automatically chooses the proper algorithm according to the current training dataset. In particular, a general evaluation method is used to assign a score for each algorithm to perform the comparison. More precisely, THOR uses *Bayes Search Cross Validation (BSCV)* [37], which can be used for all the algorithms implemented in THOR; this makes the scores obtained for the algorithms comparable, thus guaranteeing the accuracy of the results. BSCV updates the current best model during each iteration and changes the parameter settings according to the value of input *search_spaces*. The best model for the current user, which depends on its best score given by BSCV, is then generated and associated with the user.

4.3.3. Ranker

The *Ranker* is the main module to compute the recommendation results for a user. Figure 11 shows the workflow realized by the ranker. Figure 12, instead, provides the pseudo-code of the Ranker algorithm.

Figure 11 Workflow of the Ranker module

Input: username; request or JSONfile(optional) to declare the requirement of the user; new profile if the user updates their status or the user is a new user.

Output: ranked recommendations saved in table "username_response code"

```

1: function USERPREDICT(username, request, (JSONfile), (new profile))
2:   user type ← check the number of user's historical records(username)
3:   model exist tag ← check the recommender model exist or not
4:   cluster model exist tag ← check whether the cluster model exist or not
5:   response code ← automatically generate the unique code
6:
7:   if user new profile is given then
8:     user profile table in data ← update the database with new profile
9:   end if
10:
11:   if user type is old user and recommender not exist then
12:     recommender model ← train model(username,new profile)
13:   else if user type is cold user and recommender model not exist then
14:     recommender model ← copy model(predefined model)
15:   else if user type is new user then
16:     if cluster model not exist then
17:       cluster model ← train cluster model
18:       predefined model ← train model for each cluster
19:     end if
20:     recommender model ← copy model(predefined model)
21:   end if
22:
23:   offer lists ← TSP and Categorizer (request)
24:   ranked offers ← predict and rank offers (recommender model,offer lists)
25:   result table ← save results in table(ranked offers, response code)
26: end function

```

Figure 12 Ranker algorithm

The ranker initially checks the user type and trains a model if the corresponding model does not exist in the system. After getting the model, the ranker predicts if the user will buy or not any of the enriched travel offers and saves the results in a table.

If the user provides new profile information, the module updates the profile before making the recommendations; otherwise, the old version of the user profile is used, unless the user is new. After getting the profile, the system determines the type of user (new, cold, old).

If the user is new, the system needs to check whether the cluster model exists or not and train a cluster model in the latter case. After getting the predicted cluster number, the system associates the cluster recommender model with the user. If the user is not new, THOR checks if the associated recommender model exists, and, if not, it trains a new one. Finally, THOR provides the ranking of the travel offers by invoking function `API_CLASSIFIER_RESPONSE`.

Function `API_CLASSIFIER_RESPONSE` preprocesses the input data and makes the predictions by using the preference model associated with the user. Figure 13 shows its workflow.

Figure 13 Function `API_CLASSIFIER_RESPONSE` workflow

Travel offers provided by the S2R ecosystem and enriched by the Offer Categorizer and are joined with the user's current profile to form the raw system data. The function uses the One-Hot encoder to get the one-hot version data and deletes columns that do not carry any information if the number of provided records is greater than 1. Then, it reads the information about the used features (whose information is stored with the model), and reshapes the data by adding zero in the null features. The resulting data is input to the prediction function. Using the preference model associated with the user, the function, for each travel offer, computes the predicted probability of buying the offer and uses it as score of the offer.

Finally, a simple sorting function is applied to rank offers based on their score value. THOR recommends only the top 30 offers, and the information about which (if any) of these offers is bought is recorded in the historical data.

4.3.4. Performance

To the best of our knowledge in the literature, there are no other works directly comparable to THOR, thus a direct comparison of the performance of THOR with that of similar tools is not possible. An extensive experimental evaluation has been carried out and it is described in [38].

5. INCENTIVES

In this section, we describe the design of the Incentive provider module and its integration with the Agreement ledger. By providing the class diagram, explaining the responsibilities of individual classes, and by describing the agreement ledger API, we provide an overview of the algorithm that was designed to be executed by the Incentive provider.

5.1. Design of incentives

As explained in section 3.2.3, based on survey results and considering the limitations implied by the technical realisation, the R2R project narrowed the selection of incentive options for implementation to the following choices which are further used to demonstrate the mechanism of incentivisation of Travel Offer Items:

Incentive 1 – for-free **upgrade of train seat class category** that can be used in future trips,
Incentive 2 - **10% discount on a train ticket** that can be used in future trips,
Incentive 3 - **20% discount on a train ticket** that can be used in future trips.

Incentives are assigned to individual Travel Offer Items. The concept of IF-THEN rules was selected as a mechanism to determine whether a TravelOffer Item qualifies to be assigned an incentive. In practice, the rules would be proposed by actors who provide the incentive, thus typically by TSPs. For demonstration purposes, we designed and implemented the following set of IF-THEN rules:

RULE 1: IF at least one other passenger booked at least one of the ride-shares included in the Travel offer Item THEN upgrade train seat category,

RULE 2: IF at least one ride-sharing leg is involved in the Travel Offer Item THEN passenger gets 10% discount on a train ticket",

RULE 3: IF the Travel Offer Item contains at least one ride-sharing leg and the passenger previously completed at least 3 ride-sharing legs THEN passenger gets 20% discount on the train ticket".

Prior to the ranking of Travel Offers, the Incentive Provider module calculates the incentives. Figure 14 presents the class diagram implementing the algorithm followed by the Incentive Provider module.

Figure 14 Diagram of classes implementing the Incentive provider module.

The Incentive provider module receives a request to provide a list of incentives that are applicable for a Travel Offer. This request is handled by the object of the class *TravelOfferIterator*. As the incentives are allocated at the level of Travel Offer Items, the *TravelOfferIterator* loops over Travel Offer Items composing the Travel Offer and for each of them calls the function *getIncentives()* of the *IncentiveProviderManager*. Another function of the *IncentiveProviderManager* is to create a list of rules maintained by the object of the *IncentiveProvider* class. The function *getIncentives()* further calls functions *getEligibleIncentives()* and *consistencyCheck()*. The function *getEligibleIncentives()* assembles the list of incentives by looping through the *ruleList* and calling the function *isFulfilled()* of each implemented rule included in the *ruleList*. Outcome of each rule (list of applicable incentives) is appended to the list of eligible incentives allocated to the Travel Offer Item. In the next step, the list of eligible incentives is checked for consistency by the function *consistencyCheck()*. First, duplicities are removed from the list of incentives. Second, incentives that are not mutually compatible (e.g. in the case of implemented incentives it is 10% discount on a train ticket and 20% discount on a train ticket) are sorted out.

To extend the set of rules easily, rules are modelled by an abstract class *Rule*. This way also the *rulesList* is not depended on a concrete form of rules. Concrete form of rules is implemented by the child classes of the class *Rule*, i.e. in this case these are *RidesharingInvolved*, *TwoPassShared* and *ThreeBookingRS*, that are responsible for calculating rules 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Some of the rules might require data that can be provided only by some other modules. Hence, classes implementing rules may need to communicate with other modules. For a such purpose an abstract class *Communicator* was added to the class diagram. In the case of rules 1, and 3 a communication with the Agreement Ledger component is required. Such communication is ensured by an object of the class *AgreementLedgerCommunicator*. Rule 2 requires information about the mode of transport of Travel Offer Item legs. Such information can be obtained from the Offer-Cache module.

Communication with the Offer-Cache module ensures an object of the class OfferCacheCommunicator.

The information about incentives that are applicable to a given Travel Offer Item is used by the THOR module together with other attributes to classify Travel Offer Items. Moreover, it is returned together with the results of the ranking as information that can be used by the Passenger Travel Companion when presenting the Travel Offer Items. For this purpose, each type of incentive is identified by a unique string value (*incentive_ID*). A list of strings that identifies all incentives is attached to a Travel Offer. Together with other attributes characterizing a Travel Offer it is delivered as one of the inputs to the THOR module. Moreover, a list of strings that identify assigned incentives is returned together with the results of the ranking.

The Incentive provider tests IF-THEN rules at the time, when preparing the Travel Offer in response to the mobility request. Some of the proposed rules use information about bookings or the previously completed trips. Moreover, the real entitlement for a passenger to receive an incentive arises at the time, when the trip is completed. For these reasons, the integration of the Agreement Ledger component in processing of incentives is essential.

5.2. Integration with agreement ledger

The Incentives scenarios described in the previous section are linked to blockchain-based Ricardian Contracts⁸ implemented by the Agreements Ledger module. Specific endpoints exposed in the Agreements Ledger module API enable the integration of the Incentives Provider with the Agreements Ledger. The full specification of the AL API can be found in D3.5 Ride-Sharing Agreements Ledger Module.

There are two groups of operations regarding incentives in the AL API (see Figure 15), namely those related to the analysis of a Travel Offer in terms of incentives eligibility (GET endpoints) and those related to the actual creation and deployment of a Ricardian Contract for a specific ride-sharing leg (POST endpoints). The former ones are those called by the Incentive Provider and are further described in this section, while the latter ones, listed in 5.2.1, are called by the cbTSP and are described in details in the respective deliverable D3.5.

⁸ What are Ricardian Contracts? A Comprehensive Guide, <https://101blockchains.com/ricardian-contracts/>, accessed on 2022-01-13

incentive Operations about incentives

POST	<code>/incentive/upgradeSeat</code>	Enables a Ricardian Contract to upgrade the train seat of the travellers involved in the ride
POST	<code>/incentive/10discount</code>	Enables a Ricardian Contract to allow a voucher for 10% discount for the next train trip
POST	<code>/incentive/20discount</code>	Enables a Ricardian Contract to allow a voucher for 20% discount for the next train trip
GET	<code>/incentive/upgradeSeat/{travelEpisodeId}</code>	Checks if a Travel Episode is eligible for the upgradeSeat incentive (2 or more than 2 passengers in the ride)
GET	<code>/incentive/20discount/{travellerId}</code>	Checks if a Traveller is eligible for the 20discount incentive (Traveller completes 3 bookings that involve ride-sharing)

Figure 15 Operations about incentives in the AL module API

5.2.1. Ricardian Contracts generation

To facilitate the dynamic creation of Ricardian contracts through the AL module API, three RESTful endpoints are employed, one for each of the scenarios described in 5.1:

- POST - `/incentive/upgradeSeat`
- POST - `/incentive/10discount`
- POST - `/incentive/20discount`

Once one of the above endpoints is called, the data that is passed on the body of the HTTP request (see json object example bellow) are inserted into a Ricardian Contract generator which integrates them in the respective Ricardian Contract template and outputs the final Ricardian Contract. Consequently, the AL module hashes the contract using a SHA256 Secure Hash Algorithm and stores the hash and the unique id (uuid) generated for this contract on the ledger - the uuid is returned back in the server response for future reference. (see D3.5 for more information on the Ricardian Contracts of the AL module).

Example of `/incentive/upgradeSeat` JSON body request:

```
{
  "travellerId": "t0",
  "vehicleId": "v0",
  "bookingId": "b0"
}
```

5.2.2. Checking Travel Offers' Incentives eligibility

The main objective of the GET endpoints of the incentives group of the AL API (see Figure 1) is to allow the Incentive Provider to check if a specific Travel Offer qualifies for any of the incentives provided. Except for the incentive 2 (10discount) where the Incentive Provider itself handles the eligibility test, the two other incentives are checked by the Incentive Provider using the data stored in the AL. The two REST endpoints abstract complex logic behind the eligibility check and provide the result by simply returning a boolean (true or

false), denoting if the Travel Offer should get an upgraded seat or a 20% discount respectively. The two endpoints can be found below:

- GET - `/incentive/upgradeSeat/{travelEpisodeId}`

For incentive 1 in section 5.1

This endpoint returns a boolean given a travel episode id, to denote if the traveller of a specific Travel Offer qualifies for a free seat upgrade in a future trip. The condition for an upgraded seat is that at least one other passenger has already booked at least one of the ride-sharing legs included in the Travel Offer.

- GET - `/incentive/20discount/{travellerId}`

For incentive 3 in section 5.1

This endpoint will return a boolean given a traveller id, to denote if the traveller is allowed a 20% discount in a future trip. The condition for the discount is that the Travel Offer item contains at least one ride-sharing leg and the passenger has previously completed three ride-sharing legs.

The AL employs the booking, events, and other blockchain records already stored in the ledger to accommodate the above functionalities. The logic behind the `upgradeSeat` endpoint is to look for other booking records in the ledger with the same `travelEpisodeId` which means that another traveller has booked the same ride-sharing leg and will travel together in the same car. The logic behind the second GET endpoint (`20discount`) is more complex and requires a data model in the ledger for the traveller to maintain information regarding the number of ride-sharing trips of the traveller. In addition, when a traveller completes 3 ride-sharing trips the counter is reset to 0.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable, we have described the results of Task 3.2 (T3.2) - “Source Code of Algorithms for Optimal Synchronisation of Shared-Mobility and Mass Transit,” part of Workpackage 3 (WP3) of the RIDE2RAIL (R2R) project.

We have introduced a novel system to enrich and rank multimodal travel solutions proposed through the Travel Companion (TC) and match them to the specific preference of users, based on their travel history. We call this system the Offer Enricher and Ranker (OER).

We built upon the conceptualization provided in D2.4 - “Final Conceptualization of Choice Criteria and Incentives” and the work done in developing the Offer Categorizer (OC) presented in D3.1 - “Quantitative Estimate Of Service Quality Factors.”

We developed a state-of-the-art recommender system that can learn from users’ past travel history to produce a ranking of the most relevant travel offer for a given user; the system also takes into account the presence of incentives, i. e., benefits that are offered to the user to promote the usage of public transport and shared rides.

The recommender system leverages the input from three separate subsystems: the Offer Categorizer (OC) that enable the description of travel offers along 11 different categories, evaluating each trip offer along several dimensions such as comfort, environmental friendliness, and

health impact; the Incentive Provider that computes the eligibility for travel incentives; and the Data Provider retrieves user profile information and preferences to kickstart the recommender system.

This recommender system enables the implementation of a matching and ranking algorithm that also learns the user’s preferences over time based on their travel choices. Users will thus benefit from the enrichment of travel offers provided by the IP4 ecosystem and more personalized travel solutions over time.

In practical terms, the Offer Enricher and Ranker receives a set of travel offers - i.e., the proposed travel solution for a mobility request made by an IP4 user - in TRIAS format, computes the availability of incentives, and outputs a personalized ranking of the travel offers, to be presented to the user.

We highlight that the modular design of the OER, based on independent micro-services that run in isolation, follows the best industry practices for software development and should provide the best condition for future enhancements of the system.

All planned objectives of Task T3.2 have been successfully reached, and now the OC can be used as a building block for developing the other designed software components in WP3 and for the execution of the R2R demos. Furthermore, the partners involved in the task have constantly provided updates on the development so that there should be no constraints for the development of the software components coming from the design and implementation of the OER.

We would also like to stress that all the code described in this task is publicly available on GitHub under the RIDE2RAIL organization at <https://github.com/Ride2Rail>. This deliverable is intended to be a companion to the software documentation we have provided for every component, and we refer to the code repositories for the latest and most updated information.

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